

Detection and spectrophotometric determination of paracetamol with vanadium(V)

B. Sreerama Murthy*, G. V. S. R. Pavan Kumar, P. Ramana and N. Sravanthi

Department of Chemistry, Maharajah's Post Graduate College, Vizianagaram-535 002, Andhra Pradesh, India

E-mail : sreeram6000@gmail.com, prs_ganti@yahoo.co.in

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Abstract : A simple and accurate method was developed for the detection and determination of paracetamol by spectrophotometry in pharmaceutical formulations in the form of tablets. Paracetamol, was dissolved in 4 M sulphuric acid and treated with 1% aqueous sodium vanadate solution in the presence of 1 M hydrochloric acid. It exhibited a stable bluish-violet colour. The coloured compound showed λ_{\max} at 560 nm. This method is also recommended as a spot test for paracetamol. It is also precise and found to be accurate for qualitative and quantitative determinations of paracetamol.

Keywords : Paracetamol, vanadium(V), quantitative determination of paracetamol.

Introduction

Paracetamol is a widely used analgesic and antipyretic pharmaceutical compound. It belongs to the class of drugs known as aniline analgesics. It is commonly used for the relief of headaches, other minor aches, pains, inflammations and is a major ingredient in numerous cold and flu remedial combinations. While generally safe for use at a recommended dose, toxicity of paracetamol is the foremost cause of acute gastro intestinal problems. It could be considered as NSAID. Many methods for its determination were described, including chromatography, spectrophotometry and electro analytical methods. In the standard method (IP and BP), paracetamol was determined titrimetrically with Ce^{IV} in acidic medium, using ferroin as indicator. The titration was performed in cold conditions and the process of estimation, thus is time consuming. Hence a quick and accurate method is needed and developed by the authors.

During the course of experiments in search of specific colour reagents for paracetamol, it was noticed that a solution of paracetamol gave a stable bluish-violet coloured product with 1% aqueous sodium vanadate, in the presence of 1 M hydrochloric acid. A survey of literature indicated that this specific colour reaction between paracetamol and vanadium(V) was not reported previously. In view of the toxicity of the over dosage of the drug and to determine the quality, the above method of its estimation

is found to be accurate, simple, specific and will find a wide range of application in quick estimation.

Experimental

Reagents :

Paracetamol in pure form was prepared in our laboratory by acetylation of *p*-amino phenol. The prepared pure crystalline product of paracetamol was standardized by the standard method¹.

Paracetamol tablets : Ten tablets of paracetamol of each pharmaceutical company under study were weighed and ground into a fine powder. From this, a sample of 500 mg of paracetamol was weighed, mixed with about 40 ml of 4 M sulphuric acid and 50 ml of distilled water, heated to a temperature of 80 °C for 90 min. After complete dissolution, the cooled solution was filtered through a Whatman No. 40 filter paper, the solution was made up to the mark into a 100 ml volumetric flask and standardized¹.

1% Sodium vanadate solution : It was prepared by dissolving an adequate amount of an AnalaR Merck sample, in warm double distilled water.

All the other reagents used were of AnalaR grade only.

Apparatus :

An Elico-SL-177, scanning visible spectrophotometer

with recording unit and matched set of 1 cm glass or quartz cuvettes were used for recording the spectra. The weighing measurements were made by a Shimadzu-AUX-220 model digital electronic balance.

The pH-measurements were made by an Elico-LI-127 pH-meter.

Recommended procedure for the determination of paracetamol with V^V:

An aliquot of paracetamol solution (2.0 ml) was mixed with 1.0 ml of 1 M hydrochloric acid and 1 ml 1% aqueous sodium vanadate solution, to give a stable bluish-violet coloured product. The mixture was made up to 25 ml in a volumetric flask and the spectra were taken for an aliquot of the solution showed λ_{\max} at 560 nm (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Absorption spectrum of the bluish-violet coloured product obtained by the reaction between paracetamol with vanadium(V) in 1 M hydrochloric acid medium. The wave length of maximum absorption is 560 nm.

For the determination of paracetamol, an aliquot volume of paracetamol was mixed with 1.0 ml of 1 M hydrochloric acid and 1 ml of the reagent to give a stable bluish-violet coloured product and the mixture was made up to the mark. The solution was taken in an optically matched cuvette of Elico SL-177 spectrophotometer and the absorbances were measured at 560 nm. The absorbance was compared with the standard curve (Fig. 2). Beer's law was found to be obeyed up to 300 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of paracetamol (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Calibration plot for estimation of paracetamol with V^V as a chromogenic agent. Beer's law obedience is in the range of 100–300 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$.

Results and discussion

The specific colour reaction between paracetamol and V^V was studied in various concentration ranges of the reagent and acid. In very low concentrations as 1 M, the colour was found to be stable. At higher concentrations of the acid the colour appeared, but rapidly faded and hence the concentration of the acid was fixed and recommended as 1 M. The concentration of the reagent also has an appreciable effect on the colour produced. Concentration below 1% and above 1% of the reagent was prepared and the absorbance measurements were made. The bluish-violet colour produced then was not found to be stable as performed with 1% reagent solution. The colour produced with the reagent with higher concentration than 1% was observed to fade away rapidly again and was found to have an appreciable change in the absorbance measurements with respect to time. Hence the concentration of the reagent was prescribed at 1%. The λ_{\max} for the bluish-violet colour product is 560 nm (Fig. 1), with molar absorptivity, $\epsilon = 234.7 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 560 nm. There was no overlapping of the spectra of the bluish-violet coloured product of V^V and other species present in the solution. No interferences were observed. Beer's law was found to be obeyed over the range of 100–300 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of paracetamol. The standard deviation presented in the Table 1 was found to be below the prescribed limits of 2.0.

Table 1. Results of the determination of the drug in samples

Sl. no.	Drug proprietary name	PM ^a	SM ^b	SD ^c
1.	Paracetamol pure	100.12	100.15	1.2
2.	Calapol (500 mg)	98.96	99.65	0.9
3.	Parakem (500 mg)	99.02	99.58	1.2
4.	Panadol (500 mg)	98.95	99.12	1.4
5.	Crocin (500 mg)	99.67	99.32	1.1
6.	Tyfe (500 mg)	98.36	99.65	1.0

From the above said data it is clear that the proposed method for the determination of paracetamol in pharmaceutical formulations is comparable and recommended due to the advantages mentioned earlier. The standard deviation presented in the Table was found to be below the prescribed limits of 2.0.

^aProposed method. ^bStandard method. ^cStandard deviation for three sets of samples.

Conclusion :

Paracetamol solution gave a stable bluish-violet coloured product with 1% aqueous solution of sodium

vanadate in 1 M hydrochloric acid. The λ_{\max} for the bluish-violet colour product was 560 nm (Fig. 1), with molar absorptivity, $\epsilon = 234.7 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 560 nm. Beer's law was found to obeyed over the range of 100–300 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of paracetamol. This determination of paracetamol was rapid and accurate and hence is recommended. The standard deviation presented in the table was found to be below the prescribed limits of 2.0.

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References

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